

Distributed Renewable Resources Constructed With Multilevel Converter Using SVM Technique.

NAGALLA SOWJANYA, DR. D VIJAYA KUMAR

*IPG Student, Department Of EEE, AITAM, TEKKALI, AP, INDIA.

**2 Professor, HOD, Department Of EEE, AITAM, TEKKALI AP, INDIA.

1Email: sowjanya6028@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The proposed system presents power-control strategies of a grid-connected hybrid generation system with versatile power transfer. This hybrid system allows maximum utilization of freely available renewable energy sources like wind, fuel and photovoltaic energies. For this, an adaptive MPPT algorithm along with standard perturb and observes method will be used for the system.

The objective of this paper is to study a novel Multi level multistring inverter topology for DERs based DC/AC conversion system. In this study, a high step-up converter is introduced as a front-end stage to improve the conversion efficiency of conventional boost converters and to stabilize the output DC voltage of various DERs such as PV, Wind and fuel cell modules for use with the simplified newly constructed multilevel inverter. The proposed multilevel inverter requires only nine active switches instead of the twelve required in the conventional cascaded H- bridge (CCHB) multilevel inverter, control with SVM technique.

The inverter converts the DC output from non-conventional energy into useful AC power for the connected load. This hybrid system operates under normal conditions which include conventional and proposed cases of solar energy, fuel and wind energy. The proposed simulation results are presented to illustrate the operating principle, feasibility and reliability of this proposed system for Renewable resources.

Index Terms—DC/AC power conversion, multilevel inverter.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, photovoltaic (PV) energy appears quite attractive for electricity generation because of its noiseless, pollution-free, scale flexibility, and little maintenance. Because of the PV power generation dependence on sun irradiation level, ambient temperature, and unpredictable shadows, a PV-based power system should be supplemented by other alternative energy sources to ensure a reliable power supply. Fuel cells (FCs) are emerging as a promising supplementary power sources due

to their merits of cleanness, high efficiency, and high reliability. Because of long startup period and slow dynamic response weak points of FCs [1], mismatch power between the load and the FC must be managed by an energy storage system. Batteries are usually taken as storage mechanisms for smoothing output power, improving startup transitions and dynamic characteristics, and enhancing the peak power capacity [2], [3]. Combining such energy sources introduces a PV/FC/battery hybrid power system. In comparison with single-sourced systems, the hybrid power systems have the potential to provide high quality, more reliable, and efficient power. In these systems with a storage element, the bidirectional power flow capability is a key feature at the storage port. Further input power sources should have the ability of supplying the load individually and simultaneously.

Many hybrid power systems with various power electronic converters have been proposed in the literature up to now. Traditional methods that integrate different power sources to form a hybrid power system can be classified into AC coupled systems [4], [5] and ac-coupled systems [6]–[12]. However, the main shortcomings of these traditional integrating methods are complex system topology, high count of devices, high power losses, expensive cost, and large size. In recent years, several power conversion stages used in traditional hybrid systems are replaced by multi-input converters (MICs), which combine different power sources in a single power structure. These converters have received more attention in the literature because of providing simple circuit topology, centralized control, bidirectional power flow for the storage element, high reliability, and low manufacturing cost and size. In general, the systematic approach of generating MICs is introduced in [13], in which the concept of the pulsating voltage source cells and the pulsating current source cells is proposed for deriving MICs. One of the samples of these MICs is utilized in [14] to hybridize PV and wind power sources in a unified structure. Besides, a systematic method to synthesize MICs is proposed in [15]. This paper deals with two types of MICs: in the first type, only one power source is allowed to transfer energy to the load at a time,